
**TO COMPARE THE DISSATISFACTION OF ART SCIENCE, AND, COMMERCE WITH
REFERENCE TO ABSENTEEISM****Ms. Meenakshi Srivastava***Assistant Professor, S.S.Khanna Girls' Degree College, Allahabad*

The study of absenteeism is very important for any college. The word absenteeism means the absence of student from class when he is scheduled to be present at school/college. When teacher has no information in advance, that the student will not be present for class if he has taken leave to which he is entitled or on ground of sickness or in case of accident. Thus absence may be authorized or unauthorized, wilful or caused by circumstance beyond teacher's control. Absences create a dead, tiresome, unpleasant classroom environment that makes students who come to class uncomfortable and the lecturer irritable (Marburger 2001). Absenteeism disturbs the dynamic teaching-learning environment and adversely affects the overall well-being of classes (Segal 2008). Student absenteeism also causes rework and wasted time for lecturers (Lalek 1995, Rumberger 1997). In quality terms, absenteeism is a waste of educational resources, time and human potential. According to Williams (2000), students who have absenteeism problems generally suffer academically and socially. Studies indicate that students who are absent have lower achievement and may be penalized on test scores (Barker and Jansen 2000). Continued loss of instruction or poor academic achievement among students with high absenteeism is an essential characteristic of students who later dropout of school (Mayer and Mitchell 1996). In India, in almost all universities and colleges, 75% attendance is mandatory, failing which can either affect the grade of the student or even end in his failure.

In almost all the Indian universities and colleges, the rule on paper, i.e. their ordinances, spells out that a student shall not be eligible to appear in the examination if his attendance is less than 75%. Apart from this, in many institutes, marks are allotted for attendance above 75%. For example, in the BA LLB (Hons) Five year Integrated Course of Allahabad University, the students whose attendance in the prescribed subjects of study, seminar classes and computer training or any other course prescribed in the semester falls short of the required 75% shall not be allowed to appear at the examination. Also, if the student absents himself from the classes continuously for seven days, his name shall be struck off from the register. Here, in this course, there are graded marks for attendance above 75% going up to 100% so students who attend all the classes in a subject get 5 marks out of 50 marks allotted in the internal assessment of a subject. The reality check shows that even if students are chronic absentees, they are allowed to sit at the exams. In some colleges in India, even if students fail to show up for even once in the classes, they are still allowed to sit in the final exams. In such colleges, there may be a simultaneous catastrophe of professors being absent from classes too. So this leads to a vicious cycle and who leads who is led to find out? In such a system, there are less obvious hardships for teachers and students but only outwardly. The philosophy of education is stifled and the higher purpose or wholesome growth of both stakeholders, i.e. teacher and the taught, is thwarted.

Need of the study

In quality terms, absenteeism is a waste of educational resources, time and human potential. When students are absent from class, they miss valuable information resulting from peer-lecturer interaction and the benefits of the specific examples lecturers use to clarify difficult concepts. This valuable part of the learning experience cannot be replicated when lecturers re-teach the material to absentee students. Student's Absenteeism means either habitual evasion from college, or willful absence as in a strike action. Pritamkabe (2011) discovered that absenteeism in the education is a significant issue in the developing world, especially

in India it is essential that the absenteeism concern is dealt without delay. There are several causes because of which students does not attend college on regular basis. Allahabad City is a small city in Uttar Pradesh where students remain absent from college frequently. Very less number of researches has been done especially on educational issues. That's why researcher selected this area and this topic for the research. So this research will address very important issue i.e. student's absenteeism. So in order to get the clear picture of causes of absenteeism the researcher done the "TO COMPARE THE DISSATISFACTION OF ART SCIENCE ,ANDCOMMERCE WITH REFERENCE TO ABSENTEEISM.

Objective

To Compare The Dissatisfaction of Art Science, and, Commerce With Reference To Absenteeism.

Definition of Absenteeism:

Absenteeism as defined by the online [business dictionary](#) is "Voluntary nonattendance at work, without valid reason. Absenteeism also means either habitual evasion of work, or willful absence as in a strike action. It does not include involuntary or occasional absence due to valid causes, or reasons beyond one's control, such as accidents or sickness". Merriam-Webster dictionary defines it as:

1. prolonged absence of an owner from his or her property
2. Chronic absence (as from work or school); also : the rate of such absence.

Chronic absence (as from work or school); also : the rate of such absence.

Tools used in the study:

1. Dissatisfaction experienced by the college students will be measured with the help of self constructed questioner on attendance.

Methodology:

This paper is an attempt to find out the various reasons for students of not attending the college or classes during Primary as well as secondary source. The method of research is purposive survey method which is probably the best method .The population for this study was 200 students from S.S.Khanna girls degree college Allahabad .Sample size will comprise of 200 students from each faculty i.e. from art, science, commerce.Data were collected through a self constructed questioner on Attendance for examine student's dissatisfaction The Questions contains 20 questions related to a factor that causes pupils to be absent from college .The alternate responses were given for each item viz: never sometime and often a score of 1, 2 or 3 was awarded for these three responses respectively for positive item, A Score of 3,2 or 1 was awarded for never ,some time and often responses to negative item.

Statistical Techniques Used:

Percentage analysis was used.

COMPARISON OF GROUPS ART SCIENCE COMMERCE

I remain absent in the classes because of

S. No	Items	Groups	Often%	Sometimes%	Never%
1	Lack of interest in studies	Arts	3.6	23.4	9
		Science	1.8	23.4	10.8
		Commerce	0	23.4	12.6
2	Lack of personal aspiration in studies	Arts	0	12.6	23.4
		Science	1.8	12.6	21.6
		Commerce	5.4	7.2	23.6

3	Available entertainment services like malls,picture halls etc.	Arts	0	7.2	28.8
		Science	1.8	16.2	18
		Commerce	5.4	7.2	23.6
4	subjects are not according to his /her mental level	Arts	5.4	7.2	23.4
		Science	1.8	7.2	27
		Commerce	0	12.6	23.6
5	Over protection of family	Arts	7.2	19.8	9
		Science	3.6	12.6	19.8
		Commerce	5.4	7.2	23.6
6	Lack of teaching competency in teaching	Arts	0	12.6	23.4
		Science	1.8	12.6	21.6
		Commerce	0	7.2	55.8
7	Lack of self confidence	Arts	1.8	18	16.2
		Science	1.8	16.2	18
		Commerce	1.8	21.6	12.6
8	Inappropriate environment of the class	Arts	0	7.2	28.8
		Science	5.4	14.4	16.2
		Commerce	5.4	12.6	18
9	Lack of co-curricular activities in the college	Arts	7.2	10.8	18
		Science	1.8	14.4	19.8
		Commerce	3.6	16.2	16.2
10	Absence of canteen in the college	Arts	3.6	5.4	27
		Science	3.6	12.6	19.8
		Commerce	3.6	16.2	16.2

- Item 1 shows that students of Art (23.4%), Science(23.4%), Commerce(23.4%) are sometimes absent from the college because of lack of interest in studies.
- Item 2 shows that students of Art (23.6%), Science(21.6%), Commerce (23.6%) are never absent from the college because Lack of personal aspiration in studies.
- Item 3 shows that students of Art (28.8%), Science(18%), Commerce(23.6%) are never absent from the college because of Available entertainment services like malls, picture halls.
- Item 4 shows that students of Art (23.4%), Science(27%), Commerce(23.6%) are never absent from the college because of subjects are not according to his /her mental level.
- Item 5 shows that students of Art(9%), Science(19.8%), Commerce(23.6%) are never absent from the college because of Over protection of family.
- Item 6 shows that students of Art(23.4%), Science(21.6%), Commerce(55.8%) are never absent from the college because of Lack of teaching competency in teaching.
- Item 7 shows that students of Art(18%), Science(16.2%), Commerce(21.6%) are sometimes absent from the college because of Lack of self confidence.

8. Item 8 shows that students of Art(28.8%), Science(16.2%), Commerce (18%) are never absent from the college because of Inappropriate environment of the class.
9. Item 9 shows that students of Art(18%), Science(19.8%), Commerce(16.2%) are never absent from the college because of Lack of co-curricular activities in the college.
10. Item 10 shows that students of Art(27%), Science(19.8%), Commerce(16.2 %) are never absent from the college because of absence of canteen in the college.

References:

1. <http://www.childtrends.org/?indicators=student-absenteeism-ednref2>Ready,D.D.(2010). Socioeconomic disadvantage, school attendance, and early cognitive development: The differential effects of school exposure. *Sociology of Education*, 83(4), 271-286.
2. Upadhyay, P. (2013). *Emerging Trends in Indian Education*, Allahabad: ShardaPustakBhavan
3. Van Rosemalen, P. (2008). *A Learner Support Model Based on Peer Tutor Selection*,
4. Van Blerkom, M. L. (1992). *Class attendance in undergraduate courses*. *Journal of Psychology*, 126, 487-494.
5. Anandan, K. (2010). *Instructional Technology in Teacher Education*, New Delhi: A.P.H. Publishing Corporation
6. Anandan ,K. & William Dharma Rja, B. (2010). *Educational Technology*, New Delhi: A.P.H. Publishing Corporation
7. Bandhopadhyaya, A.K. (2008). *International Encyclopedia of Audio Visual Media (Vol- 1)* Delhi: Anmol Publication Pvt Ltd
- 8 The Times of India (Lucknow) Jan 15, 2015, p 2. Attendance shortage proves costly for many students
- 9 The Times of India (Hyderabad) March 26 2013, p 1
- 10 The Times of India (Delhi) Dec 28, 2015, p1.
- 11 “Biometric attendance system in varsities and colleges; Rajasthan” The Times of India (Jaipur) May 8, 2015 , p1.
- 12 Barlow, J. & Fleischer, S. (2011). Student absenteeism: Whose responsibility? *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 48 (3), 227-237.